

ANNUAL DRAINAGE VOLUMES AND NITRATE-NITROGEN LEACHING UNDER SILAGE MAIZE IN WET AND DRY YEAR

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SUMMARY: The quantity of nitrate in groundwater is affected by diffuse agricultural pollution and hence, it is strongly linked to the amount of applied nitrogen (in surplus) on agricultural land. In order to determine nitrate-nitrogen leaching in diverse precipitation conditions, lysimetric field experiment was set in 2011 in Varaždin County, Croatia. Leachate from three zero-tension pan lysimeters on agricultural plot (maize) was collected twice a month or after abundant rainfall. Research results show that 25% of total precipitation leached in 2012 and 13% in 2013. ANOVA results confirm there is a statistically significant difference in NO₃-N concentrations between hydrological dry and wet years. In dry years NO₃-N concentrations vary from 36 to 56 mg/l and in 2013 from 8 to 40 mg/l.

Key words: nitrate-nitrogen, leachate, hydrological conditions, lysimeter, maize

INTRODUCTION

Intensive loss of nitrate or high nitrate level in different water bodies has been increasing over recent decades. Highly soluble NO₃⁻, if not taken up by crops or denitrified, can be moved below the root zone and has the potential to affect the quality of groundwater. Nitrate leaching to groundwater, as one of the major concern of intensive agricultural production depends not only on the amount of nitrate in the soil profile but also on the amount of water in soil. Diverse climatic condition (precipitation seasonality) in interaction with inherent site factors, such as micro relief attributes, agricultural management practice, hydraulic soil properties and the soil biological activity cause year-to-year differences in percolation at given location. High nitrate concentration in water is one of the main reasons for drinking water quality decrease and eutrophication of surface waters and can cause serious health problems as well. Biogeochemical exchange between terrestrial ecosystems and groundwater is predominantly unidirectional in most landscapes, where downward water transport from ecosystems to aquifers (recharge) is the only flux connecting them and the primary pathway of nitrogen inputs to groundwater (Galloway et al., 2003). In these situations soil nutrients can be leached and laterally delivered to lower

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positions of the landscape via subsurface water flow (Portela et al., 2009). Understanding N exchange between crop ecosystems and groundwater becomes a crucial ecological issue, especially in intensive agricultural area. To mitigate these growing problems different action programs were designed to reduce nitrate concentration below Water Directive (80/778/EEC) limit of 50 mg l⁻¹ for nitrate (11,3 mg l⁻¹ for nitrate-nitrogen). The EU legislation had adapted The Nitrate Directive (91/676/ECC) with main goal to prevent advanced soil and water degradation caused by nitrate due to diffuse losses from agriculture. The Nitrate Directive demands that EU Member States define the catchments affected by nitrate pollution where agriculture is a significant source of nitrate pollution as Nitrate Vulnerable Zones (NVZs).

In Croatia five regions were classified as NVZs. Designation of NVZs is based on data derived from GIS database of water bodies and catchments boundaries, hydro geological map, map of natural groundwater vulnerability, available land use databases and ground, surface, transitional and coastal waters national monitoring results. Northern part of Varaždin County, in the northern Croatia, is one the delineated zones. Varaždin area represents one of the most intensive agricultural areas in Croatia: 59% of total county area is used as agricultural land. The most common agricultural production there is typical crop production (Vincek and Ernoić, 2009). There is highly developed intensive vegetable production on small family plots with an average size of 0,23 ha, which is twice as smaller than average plot size in Croatia (Statistical Yearbook of the Republic of Croatia, 2003). Also, there is a significant number of cattle and chicken farm. The stated indicates that agricultural pressures in Varaždin area are very high.

On the other hand, hydro geological conditions in this area are also very specific. The whole area is under influence of the large rivers Drava and Mura on its border, so the aquifer in this part is composed of gravel and sand with variable portions of silt (Urumović et al., 1990). The most common soil type is alluvial soil with shallow active profile mainly on gravel base. This means that the covering layer of aquifer is not continuously developed; in some parts it exceeds 2 meters and in some it completely disappears (Lavra and Marković, 2007). That is considered as favorable for aquifer recharge, but on the other hand this makes aquifer very subject to different pollutions.

There are few methods for direct nutrient and pollutant measurement and lysimeter installation is one of commonly used methods in terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems (Romić et al., 1997; Aronsson and Bergström, 2000; Romić et al., 2003; Matlou and Haynes, 2006; Bubalo et al., 2013). Field lysimeters study is set in Varaždin County on plot used for crop production (silage maize). There are some factors affecting nitrate leaching that cannot be controlled, such as precipitation and natural soil properties. However, knowledge about their impact on leaching rate and levels can optimize land management and diminish negative agricultural effects on resources pollution. So the objective of this research was to quantify and investigate annual and seasonal differences in leachate amount and N-leaching losses over a 3-year period under conventional silage maize production in northern Croatia.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

In April 2011 triplicate of zero-tension pan lysimeters (Fig. 1) was installed on rain fed silage maize plot (46°17'32"N, 16°06'31"E – according to WGS84 system) in Varaždin County, in a hilly part of the county. Since the plot has a noticeable incline, lysimeters were installed in a flatter part of the plot.

Figure 1. Location of lysimetric monitoring station in Varaždin County (Croatia)

The first step in lysimeters installation was opening the soil profiles and determining the depth of less permeable Cg horizon. The soil profile was additionally excavated at that depth so the soil layer above lysimeter remains undisturbed. PVC reinforced hose of suitable diameter is connected to lysimeter drain and is set with sufficient slope to ensure the flow of leachate. Leachate is collected in a plastic container in which the PVC pipe is built. In the same container the stiff plastic PVC pipe is vertically integrated and it has perforations along the wall to allow the pumping of the collected water. Vertical stiff PVC pipe is sealed with a plastic cap to prevent collection of rainwater and potential sources of contamination in the tank, more precisely to preserve the leachate samples. In the final stage, open pedological profiles were filled with excavated soil and additionally compacted to prevent the peripheral flow of groundwater towards the opened profile. This also enabled the unobstructed sowing, planting and technology of culture processing.

The plot was used in three consecutive years for production of silage maize. Sowing was done in third decade of April and harvest was done in second decade of September each year. Fertilization was done twice a year: manure fertilization after harvest (total N input=123 kg ha⁻¹) and additional mineral fertilization before sowing (total N input=48 kg ha⁻¹).

Soil samples, both bulk and cylinders, were collected after opening pedological profile. In cylinder samples from the genetic horizons of the profile were done the soil density test, soil capacity for water and air, and vertical water permeability of the soil (Laboratory of The Department of Amelioration, Faculty of Agriculture, Zagreb, own method). Bulk soil samples were analyzed for NO₃-N using a continuous-flow auto analyzer (Skalar San++ Analyzer, Breda, Netherlands) according to HRN ISO 14255:2004 to determine initial NO₃-N status.

Leachate samples are collected by pumping in period May 2011-December 2013 according to determined dynamics: or after abundant rainfall or twice a month. Leachate samples are collected 14 times in that period. Samples are taken and transported to the laboratory under low temperature condition and kept under that condition until the analysis. Leachate samples were analyzed for NO₃-N using a continuous-flow auto analyzer (Skalar San++ Analyzer, Breda, Netherlands). In the paper the data for leachate amount and NO₃-N concentration in leachate will be expressed as an average value from collected samples in each sampling campaign. Analysis results were analyzed by analysis of variance (ANOVA) using the SAS statistical software package (SAS Institute, 2007).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results of cylinder samples analysis showed that the soil have high porosity and high permeability (the average value of permeability coefficient K at depth of 10-15 cm is $4,1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ cm s}^{-1}$) which enables fast nutrient leakage to deeper horizons. NO₃-N content in top layer (0-35 cm) was 36 mg kg⁻¹ and there is noticeable decreasing trend with increasing depth; NO₃-N content at depth 95-130 cm was 2,0 mg kg⁻¹.

Graph 1 displays precipitation variation in research period, 30-years average annual precipitation, leachate amount and measured NO₃-N concentrations in leachate.

Total annual precipitation at meteorological station Varaždin has a 30-years average of 832 mm. In research period both hydrological situations occurred: years 2011 and 2012 were dry and year 2013 was wet, compared to 30-years average. Total annual precipitation was 414, 589 and 1103 mm, respectively. Leachate amount analysis on annual level did not include year 2011 because research was set in April, so the whole hydrological year could not be covered. Leachate amount in research period varies from 4 to 43 mm with an average of 21 mm. Minimum amount was recorded in September and October 2011 and maximum was recorded in January 2012.

Graph 1. Nitrogen-nitrate leaching (amount, mm and concentration, mg l^{-1}) and precipitation (mm)

High precipitation and plant's inability to uptake all available nitrate results in surplus nitrate leaching (Romić et al., 2003). Researches indicate that in Croatia in current climatic conditions the risk of nitrogen leaching from the topsoil is highest during the autumn and winter (Šimunić et al., 1997; Romić and Borošić, 1998). Research results show that 25% of total precipitation leached in 2012 and 13% in 2013. Leachate amount in hydrological significant precipitation period for study area - autumn (11% in October 2011, 12% in October 2012, 12% in October 2013) corresponds to the leachate amount on annual level in wet conditions (2013). Due to high precipitation in 2013, especially in autumn and winter, i.e. outside the vegetation period, the samples are collected more frequently. Maximum leachate of 30 mm in 2013 was collected in two occasions, in May and December. In that year, 4 leachate samples were larger than the average and less volumes samples were collected in spring. In hydrological dry conditions (2011 and 2012), maximum leachate amount was recorded in January 2012, which consists with the statement that the risk of nitrogen leaching from the topsoil is highest during the autumn and winter. On the other hand, in the same period two leachate samples in summer (July 2011 and June 2012) were 23 and 33 mm, larger than the average leachate sample.

Average $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ concentration in research period is 34 mg l^{-1} , which is approximately 3 times higher than maximum allowed concentration (MAC) of $11,3$

mg l⁻¹. Maximum NO₃-N concentration of 56 mg l⁻¹ was recorded in October 2011 and minimum (8 mg l⁻¹) in April 2013. It is noticeable from graph 1. that fertilization (time and amount) affects nitrate-nitrogen leaching. Manure fertilization (MF) in September (input N=123 kg ha⁻¹) causes increase in NO₃-N concentration. This increase is more stressed in a hydrological dry years and in 2013 there is even slight decrease in NO₃-N concentration after manure fertilization, which is caused by more intense leaching due to high precipitation amount. Additional mineral fertilization (AMiF) does not such impact on NO₃-N concentrations because the total N-input (48 kg ha⁻¹) is 3 times lower and NO₃-N concentration in the period after AMiF varies from 38 to 41 mg l⁻¹. Overall, NO₃-N concentration exceeds MAC in 85% samples, which indicates that fertilizer amount is abundant in given soil and precipitation conditions, especially in hydrological dry year and fertilization management, especially fertilization outside vegetation period, should be adapted to those conditions. ANOVA results confirm there is a statistically significant difference ($F(2,12)=5,77, p=0.018$) in NO₃-N concentrations between hydrological dry and wet years. In dry years NO₃-N concentrations vary from 36 to 56 mg l⁻¹ and in 2013 from 8 to 40 mg l⁻¹. A Tukey post-hoc test revealed that NO₃-N concentrations were statistically significantly lower in wet conditions in 2013 (22 ± 15.2) comparing to dry conditions in 2011 (42.4 ± 7.7 mg/l, $p = .027$) and in 2012 (41.4 ± 7.3 mg/l, $p = .035$).

CONCLUSION

Field lysimetric experiment set on maize plot in northern Croatia covered both precipitation events, hydrological dry (2011 and 2012) and wet (2013) year. In given precipitation and soil conditions, leaching rate on annual level is twice as higher in dry then in wet conditions. Leachate amount in hydrological significant precipitation period for study area (autumn) corresponds to the leachate amount on annual level in wet conditions. Average NO₃-N concentration in research period was approximately 3 times higher than MAC of 11,3 mg l⁻¹. Maximum NO₃-N concentration was recorded in dry year and minimum in wet year. Overall, statistical analysis confirms that fertilizer amount is abundant in given soil and precipitation conditions, especially in hydrological dry year and fertilization management should be adapted to those conditions.

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